

**STRETCH AND STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS IN THE HUMAN ARTERY
BASED ON TWO-LAYER MODEL CONSIDERING RESIDUAL STRESSES**

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Abstract

The objective is to know the stress distributions in the arterial walls under residual stresses based on two-layer model. Human common carotid arteries were analysed to show stress distributions at physiological and supraphysiological intraluminal pressures. The analyses for the loaded states were performed with stretch ratios with reference to a Riemannian stress-free configuration which is a 3D non-Euclidean manifold due to the non-zero Riemann curvature tensor. The experimental data obtained by other literature were used for the common carotid arteries to analyse the stretch and stress distributions in the arterial wall although kinematics is different from the literature. The stretches and stresses were calculated for the unloaded state, i.e., the residual stretches and stresses. And those at the axial stretch ratio 1.1 with reference to the unloaded state were calculated at the intraluminal pressures 16, 50, and 100 kPa. The stresses increased from the inner surface to the outer surface at all pressures analysed. These results suggest that in the human arteries the mechanical loads are mainly supported with the adventitia even though the media and intima play an important role to control of physiological functions.

Keywords

Human artery; Two-layer model; Residual stress; Riemannian stress-free configuration

1 Introduction

It has been well known that there exist residual stresses in arteries (Chuong and Fung, 1986; Fung and Liu, 1989; Klarbring et al., 2007; Takamizawa and Hayashi, 1987; Vaishnav and Vossoughi, 1987). Earlier studies noted opening angles of ring specimens of artery by a radial cut, but it has been found that residual deformations of axial strips sectioned from the arterial wall (Vossoughi, 1992; Wang and Gleason, 2010; Wang and Gleason, 2014). A straight cylindrical tube of artery with both the residual deformations of circumferential and axial strips does not have a global Euclidean stress-free configuration (Takamizawa and Nakayama, 2013a) in contrast with the case of only residual deformation of a ring opened by a radial cut. This has been shown by non-zero curvature of Riemannian stress-free configuration isometric to a set of local stress-free configurations in a sense (Takamizawa and Nakayama, 2013a). If the Riemann curvature tensor for the 3D stress-free configuration is not equal to zero, there does not exist a global stress-free configuration embedded in 3D Euclidean space. In the growth mechanics of bulk solid, the Riemannian geometry has been proposed with the modern differential geometry (Yavari, 2010).

On the other hand, it is difficult to separate animal arteries into media and adventitia. The author only knows the analyses by von Maltzahn et al. (1984) for bovine common carotid arteries and a group of Kassab (Lu et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2006) for porcine coronary arteries. The former did not consider the residual stresses and the latter articles considered only the opening angle of ring specimen. Human arteries were separated into three layers by Holzapfel et al. (2005) for strip specimens of coronary arteries. They have also determined the residual deformations of each layer using human aortas (Holzapfel et al., 2007). We have had the detailed data of the residual deformations of human common carotid arteries by Sommer et al. (2010) and a strain energy function determined by Sommer and Holzapfel (2012).

Analyses on the strain and stress distributions have been performed by many researchers (Chuong and Fung, 1983; Holzapfel et al., 2000; Takamizawa and Nakayama, 2013a, b) but there have been few studies on human arteries compared to animal ones which are usually one-layer model. One of few studies by Holzapfel and Gasser (2007) has analysed the circumferential stress distributions of human left anterior descending coronary artery of two-layer model considering the residual stresses. In the present study, the author analysed the stretch and stress distributions in the human arterial wall based on the two-layer model considering the residual stresses due to the circumferential and axial residual deformations under physiological and supraphysiological loading conditions using a strain energy function proposed by Holzapfel et al. (2005). The present analyses have shown that the stresses induced by the intraluminal pressures are mainly sustained with the adventitial layer and increased from the inner surface to the outer surface even at the supraphysiological pressures. The results might not coincide with the concept of the homeostasis of the stress distributions under physiological conditions (Rachev et al., 1996; Takamizawa and Hayashi, 1987).

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

We analysed the human common carotid arteries using data of Sommer et al. (2010) and Sommer and Holzapfel (2012). The separation into each arterial layer is difficult in animal arteries although the arteries of aged human donors are relatively easy to separate into each layer. Holzapfel et al. (2007) have separated an intact artery into three layers, i.e., intima, media, and adventitia. But it might be difficult that we separate the arterial wall into three layers to perform the pressure loading experiments. Indeed, Sommer et al. (2010) have separated into two layers, i.e., the media-intima and adventitia to determine the mechanical properties based on pressure loading experiments for cylindrical segments. Holzapfel et al. (2005) have performed the tensile experiments of coronary arteries of the three layers for the strip specimens. However, we need the data of tubular specimens with pressure loading experiments to know the distributions of stretch and stress in the vessel walls even though the experiments were limited compared to the strip specimens. In the following, we shall call internal-layer media instead of media-intima for brevity although the intima cannot be mechanically neglected for the arterial segments of aged humans.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Kinematics

There may not exist a global stress-free configuration if a material body is subject to residual stresses. There are, however, necessarily local stress-free configurations because an infinitesimally small body sectioned from the whole body without external forces is stress free, but Euclidean global stress-free body cannot be always composed of all infinitesimally small local stress-free pieces. Even in this case, we can define a Riemannian stress-free configuration for the body with residual stresses because the distance between two material points that are infinitesimally close in the local stress-free body can be determined even for the solid body with the residual stresses.

Let a set of material points of a solid body be B and 3D Euclidean space be E^3 . A mapping $\chi: B \rightarrow E^3$ is called a current configuration following Truesdell and Noll (1965). The unloaded configuration is represented by κ . We also call $\kappa(B)$ or $\chi(B)$ configuration because it does not induce any confusion.

For the unloaded configuration κ we shall define coordinates of a material point $p \in B$ by a curvilinear coordinate system $\xi = [\xi^1 \ \xi^2 \ \xi^3] = \kappa(p)$ with components of metric tensor γ_{ab} in E^3 ($a, b = 1, 2, 3$). We represent a matrix of components of metric tensor by $\hat{\gamma} = [\gamma_{ab}]$ which is symmetric and the determinant by $\gamma = \det \hat{\gamma}$, and so on. In general, the distance between two material points that are infinitesimally close in the stress-free solid body of B may be defined as follows:

$$ds^2 = \eta_{ab} d\xi^a d\xi^b = d\xi \hat{\eta} d\xi^T \quad (d\xi = [d\xi^1 \ d\xi^2 \ d\xi^3]) \quad (1)$$

where η_{ab} are components of the metric tensor of the Riemannian stress-free

configuration. If the unloaded configuration is stress free, we may take $\hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}$. However, we will later meet the case of the Riemannian stress-free configuration which is non-Euclidean for the segment of artery with the residual stresses.

For the current configuration χ we define coordinates $\mathbf{x} = [x^1 \ x^2 \ x^3] = \boldsymbol{\chi}(p)$ with components of metric tensor g_{ab} in E^3 . Each component is $x^a = x^a(p) = x^a(\boldsymbol{\kappa}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}))$. The deformation gradient of χ with reference to $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{F} = \left[\frac{\partial x^a}{\partial \xi^b} \right] \quad (2)$$

where $\partial x^a / \partial \xi^b$ represents (a, b) component of the matrix. If the material is incompressible, $\sqrt{g} \det \mathbf{F} = \sqrt{\gamma}$ is satisfied (Takamizawa and Nakayama, 2013b). The Green-Lagrange strain of the current configuration with reference to the unloaded body is provided as follows:

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{F}^T \hat{\mathbf{g}} \mathbf{F} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}) \quad (3)$$

The Green-Lagrange strain of the current configuration with reference to the Riemannian stress-free configuration is as follows:

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{F}^T \hat{\mathbf{g}} \mathbf{F} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}) \quad (4)$$

Because we treat the cylindrical tube of artery, we choose the cylindrical coordinate systems as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\xi} = [\vartheta \ \zeta \ \rho], \quad \hat{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{x} = [\theta \ z \ r], \quad \hat{\mathbf{g}} = \begin{bmatrix} r^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

We show local stress-free configurations for media and adventitia in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Schematic drawings of stress-free and unloaded configurations of media and adventitia and unloaded intact vessel are shown. Intact current configuration is also schematically drawn.

These are the idealized configurations for simplicity. We assume that the infinitesimally thin sliced sectors and narrow curled axial strips are stress free. For the unloaded configurations, the three stretch ratios in the circumferential, axial, and radial directions with reference to the local stress-free configurations are determined by the following equations (cf. Fig. 1):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Lambda_{X\vartheta} &= \frac{2\pi\rho_X}{\Theta_{X0}R_X} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{X\vartheta\vartheta}}{\eta_{X\vartheta\vartheta}}} \quad (R_{Xi} \leq R_X \leq R_{Xo}, \rho_{Xi} \leq \rho_X \leq \rho_{Xo}) \\
 \Lambda_{X\zeta} &= \frac{l_{Xu}}{\Psi_{X0}S_X} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{X\zeta\zeta}}{\eta_{X\zeta\zeta}}} \quad (S_{Xo} \leq S_X \leq S_{Xi}) \\
 \Lambda_{X\rho} &= \frac{d\rho_X}{dR_X} = -\frac{d\rho_X}{dS_X} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{X\rho\rho}}{\eta_{X\rho\rho}}} \quad (S_{Xi} - S_X = R_X - R_{Xi})
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where X denotes A (adventitia) or M (media), and ρ_X , R_X , and S_X are radii of a material point p_X in the unloaded body and stress-free ones, respectively. It should be noted that the radial distance is common from the inner surface with circumferential and axial strips. The length of l_{Xu} denotes the axial length of the unloaded segment of adventitia or media. The dimensions of the stress-free configurations of media and adventitia are shown in Table 1 from the article by Sommer et al. (2010).

Table 1 Dimensions of stress-free local configurations and unloaded lengths of segments (M : Media, A : Adventitia, $l_u=15.0$ mm). These values are means of the specimens from Sommer et al. (2010).

R_{Mi} (mm)	R_{Mo} (mm)	Θ_{M0} (deg)	S_{Mi} (mm)	Ψ_{M0} (deg)	l_u / l_{Mu}
5.567	6.267	198.3	71.779	12.3	0.98
R_{Ai} (mm)	R_{Ao} (mm)	Θ_{A0} (deg)	S_{Ai} (mm)	Ψ_{A0} (deg)	l_u / l_{Au}
3.949	4.419	323.9	8.235	99.5	1.08

From Eq. (6), we can determine the metric tensor of the Riemannian stress-free configurations of media and adventitia:

$$\eta_{X\vartheta\vartheta} = \left(\frac{\Theta_{X0} R_X}{2\pi} \right)^2, \quad \eta_{X\zeta\zeta} = \left(\frac{\Psi_{X0} S_X}{l_{Xu}} \right)^2, \quad \eta_{X\rho\rho} = \left(\frac{dR_X}{d\rho_X} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{dS_X}{d\rho_X} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{Xab} = 0 \quad (a \neq b)$$

The six independent covariant components of the Riemann curvature tensor which may not vanish in the 3D manifold are $R_{X\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\zeta}$, $R_{X\vartheta\rho\vartheta\rho}$, $R_{X\zeta\rho\zeta\rho}$, $R_{X\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\rho}$, $R_{X\zeta\vartheta\zeta\rho}$, $R_{X\rho\vartheta\rho\zeta}$ (Sokolnikoff, 1964). We have obtained as follows:

$$R_{X\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\zeta} = \left(\frac{\Theta_{X0} \Psi_{X0}}{2\pi l_{Xu}} \right)^2 R_X S_X > 0 \quad (8)$$

The other five components vanished all over the stress-free configurations for media and adventitia as shown in **Appendix**. The Riemann curvature tensor does not vanish as shown in Eq. (8), i.e., the Riemannian stress-free configurations for media and adventitia are non-Euclidean. This implies that there are no global stress-free states in 3D Euclidean space.

Deformation gradients of the media and adventitia of the unloaded configuration with reference to the stress-free configuration are provided as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_{X1} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial \xi_X^a \\ \partial \xi_X^b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The incompressibility of each arterial layer is represented by $\sqrt{\gamma_X} \det \mathbf{F}_{X1} = \sqrt{\eta_X}$. Then, we can obtain the following equation:

$$\frac{2\pi\rho_X}{\Theta_{X0}R_X} \frac{l_{Xu}}{\Psi_{X0}S_X} \frac{d\rho_X}{dR_X} = 1 \quad (S_{Xi} - S_X = R_X - R_{Xi}) \quad (10)$$

The solution is derived as follows (insert $S_X = R_{Xi} + S_{Xi} - R_X$ into the above equation):

$$\rho_X = \sqrt{\frac{\Theta_{X0}\Psi_{X0}}{6\pi l_{Xu}} \left[-2R_X^3 + 3(R_{Xi} + S_{Xi})R_X^2 - (R_{Xi} + 3S_{Xi})R_{Xi}^2 \right] + \rho_{Xi}^2} \quad (11)$$

where the angles are expressed in radian, and a boundary condition $\rho_{Xi} = \rho_X(R_{Xi})$ was imposed, and it was easily demonstrated that ρ_X increases as R_X increases for $R_X \in [R_{Xi}, R_{Xo}]$. In general, $\rho_{Mo} \neq \rho_{Ai}$ and $l_{Mu} \neq l_{Au}$. In the unloaded intact artery, the boundary between media and adventitia is ρ_m and the axial length l_u as shown in Fig.1. Equation (9) is expressed with physical components as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{X1} = \left[\sqrt{\gamma_{Xaa}} \sqrt{\eta_X^{bb}} \frac{\partial \xi_X^a}{\partial \xi_X^b} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\pi\rho_X}{\Theta_{X0}R_X} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_{Xu}}{\Psi_{X0}S_X} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{d\rho_X}{dR_X} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{not sum with } a, b) \quad (12)$$

Deformation gradients of the intact unloaded configuration with reference to each unloaded layer are provided by the following:

$$\mathbf{F}_{X2} = \left[\frac{\partial \xi^a}{\partial \xi^b} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \vartheta_X} & \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \zeta_X} & \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \rho_X} \\ \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \vartheta_X} & \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \zeta_X} & \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \rho_X} \\ \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \vartheta_X} & \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \zeta_X} & \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \rho_X} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_u}{l_{Xu}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{d\rho}{d\rho_X} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where $\vartheta = \vartheta_X$, $\zeta = (l_u / l_{Xu})\zeta_X$, and $\rho = \rho(\rho_X)$. Because the incompressibility condition is represented by $\sqrt{\gamma} \det \mathbf{F}_{X2} = \sqrt{\gamma_X}$, the following equations are obtained:

$$\rho = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_M^2 - \rho_{Mi}^2}{(l_u / l_{Mu})} + \rho_i^2}, \quad \rho_i \leq \rho \leq \rho_m = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_{Mo}^2 - \rho_{Mi}^2}{(l_u / l_{Mu})} + \rho_i^2}$$

$$\rho = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_A^2 - \rho_{Ai}^2}{(l_u / l_{Au})} + \rho_m^2}, \quad \rho_m \leq \rho \leq \rho_o = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_{Ao}^2 - \rho_{Ai}^2}{(l_u / l_{Au})} + \rho_m^2} \quad (14)$$

The physical components of the deformation gradients are expressed as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{X_2} = \left[\sqrt{\gamma_{aa}} \sqrt{\gamma_X^{bb}} \frac{\partial \xi^a}{\partial \xi_X^b} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\rho}{\rho_X} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_u}{l_{Xu}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{d\rho}{d\rho_X} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{not sum with } a, b) \quad (15)$$

The deformation gradient of a current segment with two layers with reference to the intact unloaded state is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_3 = \left[\frac{\partial x^a}{\partial \xi^{cb}} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \vartheta} & \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \rho} \\ \frac{\partial z}{\partial \vartheta} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \rho} \\ \frac{\partial r}{\partial \vartheta} & \frac{\partial r}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial r}{\partial \rho} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{l_u} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{d\rho} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Here, the incompressibility of the vessel wall is represented by $\sqrt{g} \det \mathbf{F}_3 = \sqrt{\gamma}$. We obtain the following relationship from the above incompressibility condition (Chuong and Fung, 1986):

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\rho^2 - \rho_i^2}{(l_z / l_u)} + r_i^2} \quad (17)$$

The deformation gradient of the current configuration with reference to the unloaded configuration expressed in physical components are as follows from Eq. (16):

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_3 = \left[\sqrt{g_{aa}} \sqrt{\gamma^{bb}} \frac{\partial x^a}{\partial \xi^b} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{r}{\rho} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{l_u} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{d\rho} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{not sum with } a, b) \quad (18)$$

The deformation gradient of the current configuration with reference to the Riemannian stress-free configurations is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_X = \mathbf{F}_3 \mathbf{F}_{X2} \mathbf{F}_{X1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{l_{Xu}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{d\rho_X} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The deformation gradients expressed in the physical components are as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_X = \bar{\mathbf{F}}_3 \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{X2} \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{X1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\pi r}{\Theta_{X0} R_X} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{X0} S_X} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{dR_X} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_\theta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where the medial wall is indicated by $X = M$ and the adventitial one $X = A$, and l_z is a segment length of the current configuration. There may be the stretch and stress discontinuities at the boundary between the medial and adventitial layers. The stretch ratios with reference to the stress-free configuration are denoted with λ_θ , λ_z , and λ_r , respectively. The incompressibility condition $\sqrt{g} \det \mathbf{F}_X = \sqrt{\eta_X}$ of the wall provides the following relationship:

$$\frac{2\pi r}{\Theta_{X0} R_X} \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{X0} S_X} \frac{dr}{dR_X} = 1 \quad (S_{Xi} - S_X = R_X - R_{Xi}) \quad (21)$$

The radius r of a point of the wall of the current configuration is provided as follows from the above equation:

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\Theta_{M0} \Psi_{M0}}{6\pi l_z} \left[-2R_M^3 + 3(R_{Mi} + S_{Mi})R_M^2 - (R_{Mi} + 3S_{Mi})R_{Mi}^2 \right] + r_i^2} \quad (R_M \in [R_{Mi}, R_{Mo}]) \quad (22)$$

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\Theta_{A0} \Psi_{A0}}{6\pi l_z} \left[-2R_A^3 + 3(R_{Ai} + S_{Ai})R_A^2 - (R_{Ai} + 3S_{Ai})R_{Ai}^2 \right] + r_m^2} \quad (R_A \in [R_{Ai}, R_{Ao}])$$

where the radius $r_m = r(R_{Mo})$ is calculated with the former equation in Eq. (22). In this case, there is not any gap or overlap between the media and adventitia layers. Because l_z can be expressed by the axial stretch ratio $\tilde{\lambda}_z$ with reference to the unloaded configuration, we use a relationship $l_z = \tilde{\lambda}_z l_u$. The relationship between the radius of the unloaded intact vessel and ones of stress-free states is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Relationships between radii of rings by a radial cut for dissected media and adventitia and the radius of the unloaded intact vessel.

2.2.2 Strain Energy Function

We shall use a strain energy function (Holzapfel et al., 2005) to characterise vessel layers as follows:

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2}(I-3) + \frac{k_1}{2k_2}[(\exp Q_+ - 1) + (\exp Q_- - 1)]$$

$$Q_{\pm} = k_2[(1-\zeta)(I-3)^2 + \zeta(K_{\pm} - 1)^2] \quad (23)$$

$$I = g_{ab} \frac{\partial x^a}{\partial \xi^c} \frac{\partial x^b}{\partial \xi^d} \eta^{cd}, \quad K_{\pm} = g_{ab} \frac{\partial x^a}{\partial \xi^c} \frac{\partial x^b}{\partial \xi^d} v_{\pm}^c v_{\pm}^d$$

where μ and k_1 denote constants with energy density dimension and the physical components of two unit contravariant vectors $\mathbf{v}_{\pm} = [v_{\pm}^{\vartheta} \ v_{\pm}^{\zeta} \ v_{\pm}^{\rho}]$ in the Riemannian stress-free configuration ($\mathbf{v}_{\pm} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}} \mathbf{v}_{\pm}^T = 1$) are defined with $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_+ = [\cos(+\varphi) \ \sin(+\varphi) \ 0]$ and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_- = [\cos(-\varphi) \ \sin(-\varphi) \ 0]$ in which φ denotes an angle of each mean value of fibres against the circumferential direction with a symmetric bimodal distribution, and I and K_{\pm} are invariant. Because K_{\pm} represent the contribution of the fibre components, they support only tensile stress when it is greater than 1, i.e., if $K_{\pm} \leq 1$ in computing, K_{\pm} is set 1. In the present study, \mathbf{F} has only non-zero diagonal components, but the general equations include non-zero shear strains and has the cylindrical orthotropic symmetry (Patel et al., 1969). The constant ζ is a weight of fibre component in each layer with a value between 0 and 1. Because in the present study only the diagonal components λ_{θ} ,

λ_z, λ_r may not vanish, I and K_{\pm} are expressed as follows:

$$I = \lambda_{\theta}^2 + \lambda_z^2 + \lambda_r^2, \quad K_{\pm} = \lambda_{\theta}^2 \cos^2(\pm\varphi) + \lambda_z^2 \sin^2(\pm\varphi) \quad (24)$$

The mean values of material parameters (Sommer and Holzapfel, 2012) are shown in Table 2 determined for the separated media and adventitia. We shall use these values to analyse the stretch and stress distributions in the human common carotid artery.

Table 2 Mean material parameters of strain energy function for the media and the adventitia (Sommer and Holzapfel, 2012). The last column shows the pressure ranges of the experiments.

	μ (kPa)	k_1 (kPa)	k_2	ζ	φ (deg)	
<i>Media</i>	122.3	24.7	16.5	0.8	6.9	(0-20 kPa)
<i>Adventitia</i>	138.2	178.4	48.4	0.8	25.9	(0-100 kPa)

2.2.3 Cauchy Stress

The Cauchy stress tensor for the incompressible material can be derived from the strain energy function as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = -H\hat{\mathbf{g}} + \hat{\mathbf{g}}\mathbf{F} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad (25)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\tau_{ab}]$ and H denote a matrix of covariant components of the Cauchy stress and a Lagrange multiplier for the incompressibility of the material, respectively, and the (a, b) component of $\partial W / \partial \mathbf{F}$ is defined as $\partial W / \partial (\partial x^b / \partial \xi^a)$. The physical components for τ_{ab} are denoted with σ_{ab} .

2.2.4 Equilibrium Equation of Stress

The equilibrium equation for the Cauchy stress is as follows:

$$\nabla_b \tau_a^b = \nabla_b (g^{bc} \tau_{ac}) = 0 \quad (26)$$

where ∇_b denotes covariant derivative for the curvilinear coordinate system \mathbf{x} with $\hat{\mathbf{g}}$ for 3D Euclidean space. Only the following equation for the cylindrical coordinate system is not trivial in the present study:

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{rr}}{\partial r} + \frac{\tau_{rr}}{r} - \frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r^3} = 0 \quad (27)$$

Because the physical components of the stresses are $[\sigma_{ab}] = [\sqrt{g^{aa}} \sqrt{g^{bb}} \tau_{ab}]$ (not sum with a, b), the equation for the physical components is expressed as follows (Chuong and Fung, 1986):

$$\frac{d\sigma_{rr}}{dr} + \frac{\sigma_{rr} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}}{r} = 0 \quad (28)$$

where the boundary conditions are $\sigma_{rr}(r_i) = -P_i$, $\sigma_{rr}(r_m - \varepsilon) = \sigma_{rr}(r_m + \varepsilon)$ for an infinitesimally small positive number ε , and $\sigma_{rr}(r_o) = -P_o = 0$. We can obtain the following relationships (Holzapfel et al., 2000):

$$P_i = \int_{r_i}^{r_o} (\sigma_{\theta\theta} - \sigma_{rr}) \frac{dr}{r}, \quad F_z = 2\pi \int_{r_i}^{r_o} [\sigma_{zz} - (\sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{\theta\theta}) / 2] r dr \quad (29)$$

Here, P_i and F_z denote the intraluminal pressure and the external axial force, respectively. The stresses are discontinuous at the boundary between the media and adventitia except for the radial stress. Because the straight tube with cylindrical orthotropy under only axial stretch and intraluminal pressure yields only diagonal strain in the cylindrical coordinate system (Patel et al., 1969), the diagonal Cauchy stress may be also expressed from Eq. (25) as follows:

$$\sigma_{aa} = -H + \lambda_a \frac{\partial W}{\partial \lambda_a} \quad (\text{not sum with } a = \theta, z, r) \quad (30)$$

Therefore, Eq. (29) may be expressed by the strain energy function without the undetermined Lagrange multiplier H . The Lagrange multiplier H can be determined from the solution of σ_{rr} .

3 Results

The experimental data needed to analyse the arterial walls are provided in Table 1 for dimensions and Table 2 for constitutive law. These data were from Sommer et al. (2010) and Sommer and Holzapfel (2012) as mean values of human common carotid arteries although the kinematics of the present analysis is different from theirs. It implies that the material parameters included in the strain energy functions are different if those were determined on the present kinematical theory.

3.1 Pressure vs radius and pressure vs axial stretch ratio relationships

The pressure vs radius and pressure vs axial stretch ratio relationships of the intact vessel were also calculated from 0 to 100 kPa as shown in Fig. 3. Sommer et al. (2010) and Sommer and Holzapfel (2012) did not perform the experiments from 0 to 100 kPa pressure for the intact blood vessels, but the transmural pressure of the media was less than 20 kPa at the pressure loading 100 kPa. Therefore, we calculated the curves which

are increased with the intraluminal pressure from 0 to 100 kPa.

Fig. 3 Intraluminal pressure vs outer radius (a) and intraluminal pressure vs axial stretch ratio (b) relationships for the intact tube from 0 to 100 kPa.

The present curves in Fig. 3 were calculated using the data Tables 1 and 2 which are mean values, but the examples of results shown in the papers (Sommer et al., 2010, Sommer and Holzapfel, 2012) are of the typical specimens. Therefore, the direct quantitative comparisons were impossible. The qualitative similarity between their results and the present ones were good for the intact vessel.

3.2 Residual stretch and stress distributions

The stretch and stress distributions in the unloaded layers of the artery were calculated from the data of Tables 1 and 2. The material parameters of the strain energy functions were used with the experiments of 0-20 kPa for the media and 0-100 kPa for the adventitia in Table 2.

The residual stretch ratios and stresses are shown in Fig. 4 for the material parameters derived from the experiments between 0 and 20 kPa for the media and those between 0 and 100 kPa for the adventitia. The stresses increase from the inner surface to the outer surface. The circumferential residual stress and the axial residual stress have similar distribution. In the separated media and adventitia, the former one has relatively higher circumferential residual stress (not shown) than the media of the intact vessel. This may be due to compression of the adventitia on the media.

Fig. 4 Residual stretch ratio (a) and stress (b) distributions for the intact artery calculated by the present theory.

The stretch and stress distributions calculated by the author using the theory of Sommer and Holzapfel (2012) are shown Fig. 5. They calculated the axial residual stretch as the ratio of the unloaded axial length to the middle length of the curled axial strip (see Fig. 2 and Eq. (7) in the paper by Sommer and Holzapfel (2012)). Therefore, the residual axial stretch calculated is the mean value. This is the same as the loaded states because the axial stretch is induced independently of the position of wall thickness.

Fig. 5 Residual stretch ratio (a) and stress (b) distributions for the intact artery calculated by the theory of Sommer and Holzapfel (2012).

The present theory predicts the residual axial stretch ratio increases from the inner surface to the outer surface, and the residual circumferential stretch ratio also increases from the inner surface to the outer surface.

3.3 Stretch and stress distributions under loaded states

The stretches and stresses at the intraluminal pressures of 16, 50, and 100 kPa are

calculated for the intimal vessels at the axial stretch ratio of 1.1 with reference to the unloaded state. The results are shown in Figs. 6, 7, and 8, respectively. The material parameters were used those determined in the pressure range of 0-20kPa for the media and 0-100 kPa for the adventitia. The stresses in the adventitia are high compared to media at the physiological and suprphysiological pressures although these are different from the results by Holzapfel and Gasser (2007) for the human coronary artery, and Takamizawa and Nakayama (2013b) for the porcine coronary artery both based on two-layer models which consider the circumferential residual strains estimated from the opening angle of circumferential ring by a radial cut. Besides these, the extremely high stresses in the circumferential and axial directions yield in the adventitial wall compared to the medial wall. Even at the pressure of 100 kPa, the circumferential and axial stresses are negative at the inner surface of media. And at the outer surface of the media, the circumferential and axial stresses are significantly low compared to the adventitial wall. In the present study, the load by the intraluminal pressure is mainly supported by the adventitial wall from the physiological to the suprphysiological pressures.

Fig. 6 Stretch ratio (a) and stress (b) distributions for the intact vessel at intraluminal pressure 16 kPa and axial stretch ratio 1.1 with reference to the unloaded intact vessel.

Fig. 7 Stretch ratio (a) and stress (b) distributions for the intact vessel at intraluminal pressure 50 kPa and axial stretch ratio 1.1.

Fig. 8 Stretch ratio (a) and stress (b) distributions for the intact vessel at intraluminal pressure 100 kPa and axial stretch ratio 1.1.

4. Discussion

4.1 Residual stresses

The existence of residual stresses is demonstrated with deformations induced by a cut of the unloaded body. We called these deformations the residual deformations. Human and animal arteries show generally residual deformations. When a cut body is small, it is considered stress free. We call this small body (ideally it is infinitesimally small) a local stress-free configuration. A sliced ring cut radially and a sectioned axial strip of a straight tube of artery are considered stress free. However, the globally stress-free configuration consisting of the local stress-free body may not exist in 3D Euclidean space. Even in this case, we introduce a stress-free Riemannian body that is locally isometric to every local stress-free body as shown in **Materials and methods**. This is possible only in a geometrically simple shape like a straight uniform tube. There may be a Riemannian stress-free body for a complex shape body, but it cannot generally be expressed with a simple metric tensor. The Riemannian stress-free configuration is not Euclidean except for a special case. We can show that there is a Euclidean globally stress-free configuration if the axial strip does not curl. In this case, it is a tube with a longitudinal slit. This is the same as the theory of Sommer and Holzapfel (2012).

Residual stress has effect on the stress distributions under physiological conditions, but it does not necessarily yield a homeostatic state. It was evident because the opening angle of radially cut ring of aorta strongly depends on site (Fung and Liu, 1989) even those support the same blood pressure under physiological condition. The opening angles diverse from negative to over 180 degrees (Fung and Liu, 1989).

4.2 Material parameter

The material parameter $k_2=48.4$ (Table 2) included in the suprphysiological range of strain energy function for the adventitia was significantly small compared to one determined in the physiological range. This is the cause of the low gradient from the boundary between media and adventitia to the outer surface under the physiological condition. If we used the higher value of $k_2=109.8$ determined in the physiological range (Sommer and Holzapfel, 2012), the greatly high gradient of the stress distributions was

brought (the results are not shown). However, the lower value of k_2 determined in the pressure from 0 to 100 kPa resulted in the moderate stress gradients in the adventitia.

The results of the stress distributions in the adventitia show the low gradient in the suprphysiological pressures compared to the physiological pressures. Does this mean that the homeostatic control of stresses is valid under the suprphysiological condition? But the suprphysiological pressures do not occur under ordinary conditions. The significantly higher stresses at the outer surface of the adventitia occur under the physiological blood pressures. For the porcine coronary artery there occurs the low stress in the adventitia compared to the media (Takamizawa and Nakayama, 2013b) under physiological conditions although the curl of axial strip was not considered. Is the human artery special? The reason might be that the human arteries investigated were from the high aged donors.

4.3 Limitation

The present paper is mainly focused on the technical points of the analysis of stress distributions for the arteries with the residual stresses. The arteries from younger donors could not be investigated sufficiently. We need more data for human arteries to find the difference from the animal arteries. Anyway, the human arteries might be stiff compared to the animal arteries, (of rabbit, dog, pig, and bovine, etc).

5 Conclusion

The stress distributions increased from the inner side to the outer side under the physiological and suprphysiological conditions. The main mechanical loads are supported by the adventitia. These results were different from those by Holzapfel and Gasser (2007) for the human artery and the animal artery (Takamizawa and Nakayama, 2013b) although the kind of arteries were different from the common carotid artery.

Appendix

If the Riemannian stress-free configuration is non-Euclidean, the Riemann curvature tensor is not zero and the stress-free configuration cannot be embedded in 3D Euclidean space. The covariant components of Riemann curvature tensor are defined as follows (Sokolnikoff, 1964):

$$R_{abcd} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \eta_{ad}}{\partial \xi^b \partial \xi^c} + \frac{\partial^2 \eta_{bc}}{\partial \xi^a \partial \xi^d} - \frac{\partial^2 \eta_{ac}}{\partial \xi^b \partial \xi^d} - \frac{\partial^2 \eta_{bd}}{\partial \xi^a \partial \xi^c} \right) + \eta^{ef} (\Gamma_{ead} \Gamma_{fbc} - \Gamma_{eac} \Gamma_{fbd}) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where a, b, c, d, e, f are variable sub- and super-scripts taking values of 1, 2, 3, and η^{ef} denote the reciprocal components of the metric tensor and Γ_{ead} the Christoffel symbols

of the first kind, respectively. We omit the subscript of X which denotes adventitia or media and take $\xi^1 = \vartheta$, $\xi^2 = \zeta$, $\xi^3 = \rho$.

In general, the number of distinct components of Riemann curvature tensor that may not vanish is six for 3D manifold, because a n -dimensional Riemannian manifold has $n^2(n^2-1)/12$ of distinct components (Sokolnikoff, 1964).

The Christoffel symbols of the first kind (Sokolnikoff, 1964) of the Riemannian stress-free configuration are:

$$\Gamma_{cab} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \eta_{ac}}{\partial \xi^b} + \frac{\partial \eta_{bc}}{\partial \xi^a} - \frac{\partial \eta_{ab}}{\partial \xi^c} \right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where the components of the metric tensor in the present study are as follows (Eq. (7)):

$$\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta} = \left(\frac{\Theta_0 R}{2\pi} \right)^2, \quad \eta_{\zeta\zeta} = \left(\frac{\Psi_0 S}{l_u} \right)^2, \quad \eta_{\rho\rho} = \left(\frac{dR}{d\rho} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{dS}{d\rho} \right)^2,$$

$$\eta_{ab} = 0 \quad (a \neq b)$$

The Christoffel symbols of the first kind of 3D manifold in the present study are as follows:

1) $a = b$:

$$\Gamma_{caa} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \eta_{ac}}{\partial \xi^a} + \frac{\partial \eta_{ac}}{\partial \xi^a} - \frac{\partial \eta_{aa}}{\partial \xi^c} \right) \quad (\text{not sum with } a)$$

$$i) a = c : \Gamma_{caa} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \eta_{aa}}{\partial \xi^a} \quad (\text{not sum with } a)$$

Nonvanishing case:

$$\Gamma_{\rho\rho\rho} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\rho\rho}}{d\rho}$$

$$ii) a \neq c : \Gamma_{caa} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \eta_{aa}}{\partial \xi^c} \quad (\text{not sum with } a)$$

Nonvanishing case:

$$\Gamma_{\rho\vartheta\vartheta} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta}}{d\rho}, \quad \Gamma_{\rho\zeta\zeta} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\zeta\zeta}}{d\rho}$$

2) $a \neq b$:

$$\Gamma_{cab} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \eta_{ac}}{\partial \xi^b} + \frac{\partial \eta_{bc}}{\partial \xi^a} \right)$$

$$i) a = c : \Gamma_{cab} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \eta_{aa}}{\partial \xi^b} \quad (\text{not sum with } a)$$

Nonvanishing case:

$$\Gamma_{aa\rho} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{aa}}{d\rho} \quad (a \neq \rho) \quad (\text{not sum with } a)$$

$$\Gamma_{\vartheta\vartheta\rho} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta}}{d\rho}, \quad \Gamma_{\zeta\zeta\rho} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\zeta\zeta}}{d\rho}$$

$$ii) b = c: \Gamma_{cab} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \eta_{bb}}{\partial \xi^a} \quad (\text{not sum with } b)$$

Nonvanishing case:

$$\Gamma_{\vartheta\rho\vartheta} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta}}{d\rho}, \quad \Gamma_{\zeta\rho\zeta} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\zeta\zeta}}{d\rho}$$

Therefore, the nonvanishing components of the Christoffel symbols of the first kind are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{\vartheta\vartheta\rho} &= \Gamma_{\vartheta\rho\vartheta} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta}}{d\rho} = \left(\frac{\Theta_0}{2\pi} \right)^2 R \frac{dR}{d\rho} \\ \Gamma_{\zeta\zeta\rho} &= \Gamma_{\zeta\rho\zeta} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\zeta\zeta}}{d\rho} = \left(\frac{\Psi_0}{l_u} \right)^2 S \frac{dS}{d\rho} \\ \Gamma_{\rho\vartheta\vartheta} &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta}}{d\rho} = -\left(\frac{\Theta_0}{2\pi} \right)^2 R \frac{dR}{d\rho} \\ \Gamma_{\rho\zeta\zeta} &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\zeta\zeta}}{d\rho} = -\left(\frac{\Psi_0}{l_u} \right)^2 S \frac{dS}{d\rho} \\ \Gamma_{\rho\rho\rho} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\eta_{\rho\rho}}{d\rho} = \frac{dR}{d\rho} \frac{d^2 R}{d\rho^2} = \frac{dS}{d\rho} \frac{d^2 S}{d\rho^2} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The independent covariant components of Riemann curvature tensor in 3D Riemannian manifold are $R_{\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\zeta}$, $R_{\vartheta\rho\vartheta\rho}$, $R_{\zeta\rho\zeta\rho}$, $R_{\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\rho}$, $R_{\zeta\vartheta\zeta\rho}$, $R_{\rho\vartheta\rho\zeta}$:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\zeta} &= \frac{1}{\eta_{\vartheta\vartheta}} (\Gamma_{\vartheta\vartheta\zeta} \Gamma_{\vartheta\zeta\vartheta} - \Gamma_{\vartheta\vartheta\vartheta} \Gamma_{\vartheta\zeta\zeta}) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\eta_{\zeta\zeta}} (\Gamma_{\zeta\vartheta\zeta} \Gamma_{\zeta\zeta\vartheta} - \Gamma_{\zeta\vartheta\vartheta} \Gamma_{\zeta\zeta\zeta}) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\eta_{\rho\rho}} (\Gamma_{\rho\vartheta\zeta} \Gamma_{\rho\rho\vartheta} - \Gamma_{\rho\vartheta\vartheta} \Gamma_{\rho\zeta\zeta}) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\eta_{\rho\rho}} \Gamma_{\rho\vartheta\vartheta} \Gamma_{\rho\zeta\zeta} = \left(\frac{\Theta_0 \Psi_0}{2\pi l_u} \right)^2 RS \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

By the similar calculations we can obtain the following results:

$$R_{\vartheta\rho\vartheta\rho} = R_{\zeta\rho\zeta\rho} = R_{\vartheta\zeta\vartheta\rho} = R_{\zeta\vartheta\zeta\rho} = R_{\rho\vartheta\rho\zeta} = 0 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Conflict of Interest The author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

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